

DIDACTIC PRINCIPLES OF FORMING INDEPENDENT THINKING OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article presents theoretical information about the organization and management of primary school students' critical thinking and its didactic process.*

Keywords: *critical thinking, didactic approach, didactic process, management, educational ideas, method, primary school teacher, formation of critical thinking, methodical tools.*

Critical thinking is defined as one of the main competencies or a necessary condition for the formation of components of the teacher's professional competence. Therefore, the development of critical thinking as an important professional quality of a teacher in the educational process requires the organization of diagnostics of the level of its formation.

To move on to the characteristics of diagnostic tools, it is necessary to dwell on the criteria and indicators that determine the initial level of the formation of critical thinking of primary school teachers. The substantiation of the components of critical thinking of the primary school teacher, which was carried out in the source, made it possible to determine the criteria for evaluating the levels of students' critical thinking.

The personal-motivational component is represented by the criterion of needs, which is characterized by the following values and needs of the primary school teacher:

motivation for professional self-improvement (motivation to acquire professional knowledge and build professional skills, realize the importance of professional growth);

the nature of the value attitude of the primary school teacher to the formation of critical thinking (motivational attitude to the implementation of critical thinking);

citizenship (civic consciousness, civic activity, civic position, citizenship); tolerance; communication skills.

The emotional-volitional component of critical thinking is represented by the regulatory-evaluative criterion:

independent thinking (independent formation of goals, ability to make independent decisions in conditions of uncertainty, initiative);

the ability of self-control (control of mental activity, control of emotions and behavior);

social activity and courage in expressing one's thoughts;

self-esteem;

reflexive abilities (the ability to analyze and evaluate one's thinking activity, behavior, qualities).

It is of particular importance to study the aspects related to the pedagogical process of the use of oral exercises in the development of critical thinking in students. Because goal-oriented oral questions and exercises play an important role in the development of students' logical thinking. Special attention should be paid to general didactic aspects of oral exercises. First of all, it is necessary to study their didactic classification.

Based on a certain didactic basis, the following classification of educational methods was implemented:

- educational methods based on the nature of the sources of information presentation and their perception by students. This includes oral, visual and practical methods.
- educational methods separated on the basis of didactic tasks to be solved at a certain educational stage. This includes acquisition of knowledge, formation of skills and competences, application of knowledge, creative activity, strengthening and verification of skills and competences.

Methods based on determining different levels of knowledge of students. Such methods include illustrative explanation, reproductive, problem statement, heuristic and research methods. This system of didactic methods includes 7 general problem-developing educational methods (monologue, dialogue, demonstration, heuristic, research, algorithmic, programmed) and 5 binary methods, that is, teaching and reading (informative-reporting method of teaching and performing method of reading, the explanatory and reproductive method of teaching, the stimulating method of teaching and the partial research method of learning, the inviting method of teaching and the research method of learning, the instructional method of teaching and the practical method of learning).

According to didactic approaches, educational methods are divided into three groups:

- methods of organizing educational activities;
- methods of encouraging and motivating to study;
- methods of monitoring the effectiveness of educational activities and self-control.

The methods belonging to each of the above groups include specific educational methods. For example, oral, visual and practical methods are used in the organization of educational activities (first group methods). This ensures that educational information is presented by the teacher and perceived by students through hearing, observation, and practical behavior.

Specialists included cognitive games, debates, incentives, etc. among the methods in the second group, and oral, written, laboratory work, individual and total control in the third group.

Literature analysis shows that many educational methods are used in practice. During our research, we used a classification of educational methods similar to the first and third groups above, but wider than them.

Forms of teacher and student activity are shown in the initial classification. The methods belonging to the third group that we are analyzing arise from the content of this activity.

It is known that the content and forms of the pedagogical process are interrelated. Therefore, the essence of the process can be understood only by taking into account its content and form. It follows from this that in the description and composition of educational methods, it is necessary to pay attention to the proportionality of the content and forms of teacher-student activities.

Critical thinking means showing curiosity and using research methods. Critical thinking involves developing a point of view on a particular issue and defending that point of view with logical arguments. Having critical thinking, a person becomes familiar with one or another idea and considers the possible consequences of their implementation. On the basis of critical thinking, the traditional cognitive process acquires individuality and becomes conscious, continuous and productive.

The theoretical analysis of the literature devoted to the formation of students' critical thinking testifies to the fact that there is no unanimity in the views of designers and figures of pedagogic science in understanding its many aspects, including the essence of primary school students' critical thinking in the educational process. Also, the problem is that they differ in the details of the interpretation of the essence.

The development of critical thinking in the learner allows to assess the situation, make informed decisions, understand the content of the changing complex life, and create conditions for personal growth. There are many methodological tools that allow the development of critical thinking. Most of them are used by the teacher in the form of innovative teaching methods. It is important to use them systematically and purposefully. In this case, the task of the teacher is to act towards the learner and satisfy his needs. The teacher should organize independent thinking activities of students. The learner should give ideas, evaluate the activities of independent or small group members. The main difference between the innovative teaching method and the normative teaching method is that it develops all the potential abilities of a person. It should be noted that the normative teaching method and the innovative teaching method look at the future differently.

The following conditions are necessary for the development of critical thinking in students:

- time and opportunity to gain experiences in critical thinking;
- to support the activity of learners in the educational process;
- acceptance of different ideas and opinions;
- to convince students not to fall into a ridiculous situation;
- to inculcate the idea that every student is capable of critical thinking;
- supporting forms of critical thinking.

Tools that form critical thinking appear as a system only when the choice is made, taking into account the specific goals of each stage in the educational process, and they together affect each component of critical thinking of primary school students. The content of critical thinking is connected through three external factors: object, purpose, didactic principles development. What should be understood by the didactic basis of the formation of critical thinking of primary school students? We understand this concept as follows:

1. Justify the goals of critical thinking.
2. Development of scientifically based and practical forms of students' critical thinking.
3. Scientific development of the formation of lesson motives.
4. Scientific development of the content of critical thinking of primary school students.
5. Scientific development of teaching methods, that is, scientific development of systems of methods of formation of critical thinking and methods of teaching students.
6. Development of a system of tools for forming students' critical thinking - textbooks, didactic materials, visual aids and technical tools.
7. Scientific development of organizing and managing critical thinking of primary school students.

The formation of critical thinking of elementary school students is a complex and long-term process. It is formed in the joint work of the teacher and the student. On this basis, on the basis of critical thinking, there is an opportunity to jointly consider all important components of the formation of critical thinking of primary school students.

In conclusion, providing motivations, methods and organizational means of forming students' active critical thinking requires the need for deep research at different age stages of human development.

REFERENCES

1. Ходжаева Ф.О. Ўқувчиларни танқидий фикрлашга ўргатиш ва унинг муҳим жиҳатлари. /"Замонавий таълим" журнали/, 2017 йил, № 6, 43-47 б.
2. Каримова В.М. Суннатова Р. ва бошқалар. Мустақил фикрлаш. Академик лицейлар ва касб-ҳунар коллежлари учун ўқув қўлланма.- Т.: Шарқ, 2000.- 112 б.
3. Адизов Б.Р. Бошланғич таълимни ижодий ташкил этишнинг назарий асослари. Пед. фанл. докт. илм. дараж. олиш учун ёзилган дисс. –Т.: 2003. -280 б.
4. У.Д.Қодиров. Талаба-ёшларнинг мустақил таълим олиш фаолиятини ташкил этиш технологияси. “Талаба-ёшларни мустақил таълим олишга йўналтиришнинг педагогик-психологик хусусиятлари” мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий конференция материаллари. 2023 йил 27 май.
5. R.A.Mavlonova, N.H.Rahmonqulova, K.O.Matnazarova, M.K.Shirinov, S.Hafizov. “Umumiy pedagogika” – Toshkent, “Fan va texnologiya” nashriyoti, 2018-yil, 530-bet, 210-bet.
6. Kadirov U. FACTORS AND IMPORTANCE OF FORMING PERSONAL CONSCIOUSNESS IN THE INFORMATION SOCIETY. American Journal of Pedagogical and Educational Research. Volume 18, | November,2023.